

Sustain Sahel

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Deliverable 7.1. Landscape analysis and suitability of CSL systems

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Abbreviations

°C	Degré Celsius
CFA	Correspondence Factor Analysis
CGLS	Copernicus Global Land Service
CILSS	Comité permanent Inter-États de Lutte contre la Sécheresse dans le Sahel
CIRAD	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche
CSE	Centre de Suivi Ecologique
CSL	Crops, Shrubs, Livestock
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
FAO	<i>Food and Agriculture Organisation</i>
g/ka	Grams/Kilograms
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
LC	Land cover
LCC	Land Cover Classification
LUCIA	Land Use Change Impact Assessment tool
m	meters
Mg	Magnesium
mm	milimeter
N.B.	<i>Nota Bene</i>
Na	Sodium
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NASA-USGS	National Aeronautics and Space Administrator - United States Geological Survey
ORNL DAAC	Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
QGIS	QuantumGIS
RFE	Rainfall estimates.
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
TAMSAT	Tropical Applications Meteorology SATellite
TBP	Total Biomass Production
UKAS	Université de Kassel
WaPOR	Water Productivity Open-access portal
WGS	World Geodetic System
WP	Work Package
WRB	World Reference Base

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I. Executive summary

This work characterizes the landscape and proposes mapping of CSL suitability for the SustainSahel sites. Rainfall, elevation, soil groups, soil organic carbon and land cover-tree/shrub cover were mapped at the regional scale (Senegal, Mali, Burkina Faso) and at the site scale (i.e. 7 study sites). Data were obtained from existing databases (e.g., WaPOR, ISRIC, TAMSAT) and processed with R and Qgis software. The results show that averaged annual rainfall varies from 400 mm in Ouarkhokh to 900 mm in Sikasso. The elevation varies from less than 150 m in Senegal to more than 500 m in Burkina Faso. The dominant soil classes in the region are Acrisols, Luvisols, arenosols, plinthosols, leptosols and vertisols. Land cover is dominated by rain-fed crops and shrublands. Waterholes, Built-up and unclassified vegetation types are present in some areas. The amount of soil organic carbon ranges from 0 to 34 g/kg. The lowest values were found in Senegal at Niakhar, Ouarkhokh and Koussanar sites, while the highest values were observed at Sikasso and Koulikoro sites in Mali. At Burkina Faso sites, the intermediary amount of carbon ranged from 2 to 24g/kg.

A provisional mapping of CSL systems in the study sites was proposed. It is based on the list of woody species identified from the literature and the Work Package 4 second deliverable and on average values of rainfall, aboveground biomass, elevation, soil organic carbon and tree-shrub cover. Two tables were produced, one on the presence of species according to the sites and another on the average values of environmental parameters according to the different sites. A Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA) and a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were respectively performed using the R software to show the similarities between sites with respect to species on the one hand and environmental variables on the other hand. The results showed that species are concentrated in sites with high values of elevation, soil organic carbon, aboveground biomass, tree-shrub cover and precipitation. The preliminary analysis presented in this internal report will be further refined in coming months using additional data from WP4, 5 and 6, outputs from the LUCIA model and also advanced methods based on remote sensing technologies.

2. Introduction

This report is the first deliverable of the WP7 (D7.1). As an internal report, the main purpose was to provide a landscape characterisation focusing on the extent and suitability of CSL systems based on literature, previous projects, and other WPs' baseline inventories. Therefore, it presents a landscape description into the seven studied sites represented each by a 30km x 30km box (Figure 1), and at broader scale of the three countries of the SustainSahel project, using the main biophysical and environmental variables.

Figure 1: Location of study countries and sites of SustainSahel project

3. Data and methods

3.1 Geospatial data acquisition, processing and mapping

Most of the data used in this report were acquired from global geospatial datasets; available online and freely accessible (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). The processing included mainly mosaics creation, vector conversion into raster, resampling data to a common spatial resolution, sub-setting spectral bands of interest, band math (i.e. sum and mean calculation) and contour extraction. All these data were processed using the R programming software version 4.1.1 (<https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/base/>) and mapped via QGIS version 3.20.3 (<https://qgis.org/en/site/forusers/download.html>).

Table 1: Geospatial Datasets used in this report

N°	Data	Format (Unit)	Resolution (m)	Database	Spatial Reference System	Spatial extent	Links
1	Soil groups	Raster Dataset (-)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Country	https://soilgrids.org/
2	Soil Organic Carbon	Raster Dataset (g/kg)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Per site	https://soilgrids.org/
3	Coarse Fragments	Raster Dataset (g/kg)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Per site	https://soilgrids.org/
4	Silt	Raster Dataset (%)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Per site	https://soilgrids.org/
5	Sand	Raster Dataset (%)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Per site	https://soilgrids.org/
6	Clay	Raster Dataset (%)	250	International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Per site	https://soilgrids.org/
7	Above Ground Biomass	Raster Dataset (kg/ha)	100	Water Productivity Open-access portal (WaPOR 2.1)	EPSG:4326 - WGS84 - Geographic Coordinate System (lat/long)	Country	https://wapor.apps.fao.org/catalog/WAPOR_2/2/L2_TBP_S
8	Tree and shrubs cover	Raster Datasets (%)	100	Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center (ORNL DAAC)	EPSG:4326 - WGS84 - Geographic Coordinate System (lat/long)	Country	https://daac.ornl.gov/cgi-bin/dsviewer.pl?ds_id=1832
9	Digital elevation model	Raster Dataset (m)	30	National Aeronautics and Space Administrator - United States Geological Survey NASA-USGS	WGS 1984 Lambert azimuthal Equal Area	Country	https://certmapper.cr.usgs.gov/data/apps/world-maps/
10	Land cover classification	Raster Dataset (-)	100	Water Productivity Open-access portal (WaPOR 2.1)	EPSG:4326 - WGS84 - Geographic Coordinate System (lat/long)	Country	https://wapor.apps.fao.org/catalog/WAPOR_2/2/L2_LCC_A
11	Rainfall estimate (June-October total rainfall averaged between 2011-2020)	Raster Dataset (mm)	4000	Tropical Applications Meteorology SATellite (TAMSAT)	EPSG:4326 - WGS84 - Geographic Coordinate System (lat/long)	Country	https://www.tamsat.org.uk/data

3.2. Statistical analysis and CSL systems mapping

A provisional mapping of CSL systems in the study sites was proposed. It is based on the list of woody species identified from the literature as well as in the deliverable 2 of WP4 i.e. (Sousa et al., 2021) and the average values of rainfall, above ground biomass, altitude, soil organic carbon stock and trees-shrubs cover across the 30 km x 30 km of the study sites. Two tables were produced, one on the presence of species according to the sites (Appendix 1) and the other on the average values of these biophysical variables according to the different sites (Appendix 2).

A Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA) and a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were respectively carried out using R software to highlight the similarities between the sites in association with the species on one side and with the environmental parameters on the other.

4. Results

4.1. Landscape characterisation at large scale

The three countries covered by SustainSahel are all members of the Permanent Inter-State Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel (CILSS). Therefore, they are all sharing the Sahelian conditions mainly characterised by its tropical arid to semi-arid climate, controlled by the Gulf of Guinea monsoon and the Saharan Harmattan. Due to the high variation of the rainfall distribution during the rainy season and its redistribution by runoff on the soil surface, there is a strong diversity of plant cover and its production from one country to another and from one region to another in the Sahel. Indeed, the nuances of the soil water regime which result from the interaction between rainwater redistribution and soil texture are the basis for a strong differentiation of plant communities, in particular their perennial component i.e., trees and shrubs (Hiernaux and Le Houérou, 2006). Therefore, characterizing the behavior of biophysical and environmental variables that govern conditions at the local level (e.g., country or region) is important to improve our understanding of the functioning and evolution of Sahelian ecosystems. The analysed variables are rainfall, land cover classes, trees/shrubs cover, elevation and soil groups. Additional variables are provided as appendix (i.e.

Appendix 3-6).

4.1.1. Rainfall distribution

The annual amount of rainfall increases from the north to the south with the minimum value of 100 mm in the arid area of Mali and the maximum value in the south-east of Senegal (Figure 2). Ouarkhokh site is the driest site with annual rainfall around 400 mm while Sikasso is the wettest with around 900 mm. In an

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increasing order, the annual sum of precipitation about 500 mm in Niakhar, 600 mm in Yilou, 700 mm in Koussanar and Saria and 800 mm in Koulikoro.

Figure 2 : Seasonal total (June-October) of rainfall (and isohyets) averaged for the period 2011 and 2020 across Burkina Faso, Mali and Senegal. RFE = Rainfall estimates.

4.1.2. Land cover classes and trees/shrubs cover

The study area is dominated by grasslands located in the northern areas of the three countries, followed by shrublands present in the central part and tree covered vegetation which occupies the southern and most humid areas (Figure 3a). The rain-fed croplands are mixed with these three classes around the seven study sites. The irrigated croplands are mainly concentrated in the Senegal River delta and around the Inner Niger Delta. The driest site, Ouarkhokh, is located in the grasslands while the wettest site, Sikasso, is around the tree covered units. This situation is confirmed by the trees and shrubs cover map (Figure 3b).

Figure 3: a) Land cover classes and b) Trees and shrubs cover variation across the SustainSahel countries (i.e., Burkina Faso, Mali and Senegal). LC = Land cover; CGLS = Copernicus Global Land Service. N.B.: The trees and shrubs cover map does not reach the northern part of Mali (Brandt et al., 2020).

4.1.3. Soil classes

The dominant soil groups are respectively the Arenosols, Acrisols, Leptosols, Lixisols, Gleysols and Vertisols (Figure 4). To the exception of Ouarkhokh and Niakhar (mainly Arenosol), the project sites seem to be located in Acrisols which are present in the central part of the three countries.

Figure 4: The main soil groups into the SustainSahel countries (i.e., Burkina Faso, Mali and Senegal). WRB = World Reference Base 2006. ISRIC = International Soil Reference and Information Centre.

4.1.4. Landform variation

A clear discrepancy exists between Senegal on one side and Mali – Burkina Faso on the other side (Figure 5). The Senegalese sites are characterised by low elevation not exceeding 150 m as Senegalese-Mauritanian

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basin, while the study sites in Burkina Faso and Mali are characterised by high elevations between 300 m (i.e., Yilou and Saria) and 400 m (i.e., Sikasso and Koulikoro).

Figure 5: Elevation variation into the SustainSahel countries (i.e., Burkina Faso, Mali and Senegal). NASA = National Aeronautics and Space Administration. SRTM = Shuttle Radar Topography Mission.

4.2. Landscape characterisation by study site

This first level of characterisation of the landscape by project site was done using biophysical variables, namely land cover, soil properties (i.e., soil groups and carbon content), vegetation characteristics (i.e., tree and shrub cover) and landform variation (i.e., elevation).

4.2.1. Burkina Faso

4.2.1.1. Yilou

4.2.1.1.1. Description of biophysical variables

Yilou site is located in the Sudano-Sahelian part of Burkina Faso, characterized by an average rainfall around 600 mm per year. The area includes two types of seasons, a dry season that extends from October to May, with average temperatures that can reach 40°C, and a four-month rainy season that runs from June to September.

It presents a low topographic zone that crosses the area from east to west. In the northern and southern zones, the topography is relatively uniform, with differences in elevation not exceeding 25 m (Figure 6a).

The main soils groups are Acrisols, Vertisols, Lixisols, Gleysols and Cambisols. All of these classes, to the exception of Acrisols, occur in a mosaic in the low-lying topographic area of the village of Yilou and in the northwest of the study area (Figure 6b).

Land use mapping shows that the landscape can be divided into shrubland, herbaceous vegetation, cropland, built-up area, pond, bare soil/sparse vegetation, open vegetation and grassland. Crops and shrubs

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are the most important units, located on the plateaus. Herbaceous and tree vegetation are mainly located around the humid areas, e.g., water bodies (Figure 6c).

The amount of carbon stored in the soil varies from 2 to 24 g/kg (Figure 6d). This stock seems to depend on soil and land cover types. The content is low in Acrisols and Luvisols (2 to 10 g/kg), while values around 10 and 24 g/kg are found in Gleysols and Vertisols.

Figure 6: Variation of biophysical variables in the Yilou site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon in g/ka.

4.2.1.1.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock Systems

In the Yilou zone, the agroforestry system consists of hut fields (i.e., fields surrounding the dwellings) where red and white sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) and maize (*Zea mays*) are grown in order of importance. These fields are either collective plots of land called "zakpougo", which are under the responsibility of the head of the family, or individual plots of land called "Beologa", which belong to the active members of the family (Bonzy, 2002). In the bush fields (i.e., fields located in the bush far from dwellings), we find millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*), cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), peas (*Pisum sativum*) and sesame (*Sesamum indicum*). The average size of bush fields is estimated at about 4.5 ha per farm and 1 ha for hut fields (Sanon et al., 2014). Crop residues from the bush fields are left on site for mulching (they also constitute additional fodder for the farm's animals), while those from the hut fields are collected and stored in sheds for cattle feed and for various domestic uses such as the manufacture of ash, the use as firewood, etc.

Yilou region is characterised by a sedentary livestock farming where the animals are left to roam after the harvest to benefit from crop residues (Tittonell et al., 2012). Guarding by children and stabling of animals in fallow land happen during the rainy season.

Fallow lands are maintained for the benefits they provide such as fodder for animals, wild fruits and berries to improve daily life, wood for construction or for making tool handle, collecting leaves and bark for pharmacopoeia, etc. The provision of these products is the primary reason for maintaining fallow land, well before soil regeneration. The main woody species identified in the fallow systems are says A.

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macrostachya, *Combretum micranthum*, *Guiera*, *Lanea microcarpa*, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Piliostigma reticulatum* (Nicolay and Djamen, 2021).

The most appreciated species in the crop fields are *Vitellaria paradoxa*, *Adansonia digitata*, *Faidherbia albida* (Zangtinda, 2014) which constitute a good fodder and allow keeping cattle in the fields during the dry season who participate by its dejections in the amendment. Other species such as *Eucalyptus camadulensis*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, and *Acacia nilotica* are also present in the fields.

4.2.1.2. Saria

4.2.1.2.1. Description of biophysical variables

Saria site is located in the center-west of Burkina Faso in the Ouagadougou region. The climate is north Sudanian, with an average annual rainfall around 800 mm.

The landform is characterised by plateaus, dunes and lowlands. The dunes are located in the east, while the lowlands are observed in the western and northern areas (Figure 7a).

The main soil groups are Acrisols, Vertisols, Gleysols, Lixisols, Plinthosols and Cambisols (Figure 7b). The Acrisols are dominant and mostly located on the plateaus. They are followed by Plinthosols, which are observed in the southeastern part close to the dunes, while Gleysols and Lixisols are located in isolated units in the lower topographic zones.

As shown in Figure 7c, the Saria area is dominated by five land cover units which are croplands, built-up, shrubs, herbaceous vegetation and tree open vegetation. Their spatial distribution is as follows: shrubs and croplands (i.e., rain-fed) are dominant and scattered across the study area, while the other classes are found as isolated mosaics.

Soil organic carbon evaluated at Saria varies between 2 and 10 g/kg across the site (Figure 7d). Small variations are observed only in the northern part of the site.

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Figure 7: Variation of biophysical variables in the Saria site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

4.2.1.2.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock systems

In the Saria region, the existing agroforestry system are composed of lowland fields, gardens and dry season orchards in addition to the human settlements, hut fields, bush fields, and grazing areas (Gonzaque, 1994).

In the Saria region, the agroforestry system is composed of lowland fields, gardens and dry season orchards in addition to the habitats, hut fields, bush fields, and grazing areas (Gonzaque, 1994).

According to Singiranko (1990), hut fields are small areas permanently manured with domestic waste or animal dung collected from the human settlements and the poultry house. Thanks to this organic manure, the "hut fields" are cultivated each year according to almost unchanging methods, with food plants following in their wake. Sorghum, sown in rows, occupies most of the field and is frequently associated with cowpeas. Often the sorghum and millet rows are interspersed in varying proportions. A slight ridging at the foot of the stalks is barely noticeable. Towards the periphery of the field, we note the presence of sauce plants, especially okra and sorrel. In the bush fields, all the arable lands are cleared, with groundnuts and ground peas being the main crops grown. In the rainy season, the lowland fields are used for rice cultivation, while in the dry season, the landscape is reduced to small gardens arranged for the circumstance and a few off-season crops supplemented by mango and guava orchards.

The tree component in the hut fields is mainly dominated by *Parkia biglobosa* and *Vitellaria paradoxa* followed by other protected tree species such as *Faidherbia albida*, *Lannea microcarpa*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Adansonia digitata* and *Khaya senegalensis*. The shrub layer is dominated by sparse thickets of Combretaceae including *Guiera senegalensis*, *Combretum nigricans* and Ceasalpiniaceae including *Piliostigma reticulatum*.

In pasture areas, the tree species inventoried by Koala et al. (2021) were *Parkia biglobosa*, *Vitellaria paradoxa*, *Lannea microcarpa*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Khaya senegalensis* and *Azadirachta indica* while for shrubs,

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the most common species were *Guiera senegalensis*, *Ximania americana*, *Combretum micranthum*, *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *Acacia macrostachya* and *Acacia pennata*.

4.2.2. Mali

4.2.2.1. Koulikoro

4.2.2.1.1. Description of biophysical variables

The topographic organization of the region is quite simple. Altitudes below 370 m, gradually change from north to northwest and from south to southeast with a maximum altitude of 540 m (Figure 8a).

As shown in Figure 8b, the soil groups are spatially very heterogenous but the most visible are: i) Acrisols, which are mainly located in the eastern part of the area; ii) Vertisols present in the northern part where they form mosaics with Lixisols, Leptosols, Gleysols and Acrisols; iii) Leptosols are mainly observed along a slanting belt which crosses the area from north-east to south-west; iv) Plinthosols or leached tropical ferruginous soils interspersed with pseudo-gley are located in the northern part of the site on very small patches.

Koulikoro site is dominated by croplands (mostly present in the north and along the south-east river, i.e., lower topographic area) and shrublands scattered across the study area (Figure 8c). Tree covered units are mainly located on the higher elevation areas.

Koulikoro site showed the highest soil organic carbon values which vary from 2 to 42g/kg (Figure 8d). SOC quantity appears to be related to soil types. In the rain-fed croplands, stocks are low and range from 2 to 10 g/kg. The highest values was found in tree open vegetation areas (18 - 34 g/kg).

Figure 8: Variation of biophysical variables at Koulikoro site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

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4.2.2.1.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock systems

In the Koulikoro region, the system of "hut fields, bush fields and grazing" has evolved into a system where grazing areas are relegated to permanently uncultivated land (especially on areas with armourestones) and fallow land is almost non-existent (Benkahla, 2002).

The hut fields concentrate the majority of cultivated land. Annual crops such as millet, sorghum, cowpeas, groundnuts, fonio (*Digitaria spp.*), are associated with various trees planted or preserved after the clearing of the original forest such as mango (*Mangifera indica*), Parkia biglobosa, cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*), karité (*Butyrospermum parkii*), bramble trees (*Borassus aethiopum*), tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*), balanzans (*Acacia albida*), kapok (*Bombax costatum*) and baobab (*Adansonia digitata*) (Dolumbia et al., 2020). Cotton is also grown in this area. The organization of the crops is more or less concentric with a radius of up to 2 to 3 km from the village and the fields are open and left to the divagation of animals during the dry season (Benkahla, 2002).

The bush fields are located in the hydromorphic basins and on the bank bulges. In the lowlands, flooded rain-fed rice is grown on small, open plots. In the dry season, animals roam around and take advantage of the grass and sparse woody plants that grow in this hydromorphic zone. The main crops grown on the ridges are tomatoes, cucumbers, okra, chili peppers, eggplant and melons. On the flatter side, maize and few trees (e.g., mango, néré, and bramble) are often found. The rainy season grazing areas are made up of classified forests and areas of cuirasses.

4.2.2.2. Sikasso

4.2.2.2.1. Description of biophysical variables

Sikasso is characterised by a tropical-sudanian climate, and divided into two climatic zones: i) the humid Sudanian zone, and ii) the Guinean zone. Sikasso is the wettest region in Mali and receives averaged rainfall between 700 and 1,500 mm/year. The average annual temperature is 27°C.

The relief appears very rugged in the Sikasso site, with altitudes around 321 m in the eastern part and close to 500 m in the western part (Figure 9a).

Five soil types were identified in the Sikasso area (Figure 9b): i) Acrisols are dominant and located in the western part; ii) Vertisols, located around the low topographic zones; iii) Lixisols and Luvisols form mosaics around the Vertisols in the northern part of the site; iv) Plinthosols which correspond to leached tropical ferruginous soils with a silty or sandy-silty texture that changes to silty-clay at depth, are mainly located in the north.

Land cover at the Sikasso site is divided into seven units (Figure 9c): croplands, herbaceous vegetation, built-up, shrublands, aquatic vegetation, closed deciduous vegetation, and open vegetation of unclassified type. The rain-fed croplands are the dominant landscape unit, located in the northern and southeastern parts of Sikasso. Shrublands, closed deciduous vegetation, herbaceous vegetation, and open vegetation are clustered on the higher elevations. The built-up areas are located close to the cultivated zones, while the irrigated croplands are mostly present in the southeast along the main river.

Soil organic carbon stored in the Sikasso site ranges from 2 to 34 g/kg (Figure 9d). The lowest values (2 - 10g/kg) are found in the rain-fed croplands and shrubs, while the intermediate and high values are observed in the tree vegetation.

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Figure 9: Variation of biophysical variables at Sikasso site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

4.2.2.2.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock Systems

In the Sikasso region, the agroforestry system is present throughout the territory and is divided into hut fields, bush fields and grazing areas (Dufumier, 2005). The hut fields, close to the houses, are constantly cultivated, with a low density of woody plants and a contribution of organic manure produced by grazing animals. The intermediate and bush fields are located at a greater distance from the village and are characterized by the practice of traditional fallowing for which there is less input of organic manure (Sogodogo et al., 2014). These fields provide place for domestic animals to graze and for people to collect wood and non-timber forest products (e.g., fruits, medicinal plants, etc.).

Vitellaria paradoxa is the characteristic tree of fields in Sikasso (Kouyate et al., 2020). But there are also *Isobrerlinia doka*, *Terminalia mollis* and *Parkia biglobosa*. The shrubby species present are *Guiera senegalensis* and *Acacia macrostachya*. These fields are the result of the clearing of *Isobrerlinia doka* forest with a cultivation period of less than 5 years. Woody vegetation in fallow areas is dominated by *Guiera senegalensis*, *Combretum micranthum*, *Pteleopsis suberosa*, *Terminalia mollis* and *Piliostigma thonningii* (Ministère de l'Agriculture, 2008).

Agricultural systems in Sikasso are dominated by cotton cultivation on the slopes and corn cultivation in the south (Blanchard, 2010). Dry cereals, millet and sorghum, are well represented in the north of the zone. Legume crops (e.g. groundnuts, cowpeas) and lowland crops are used as diversification crops.

Livestock production systems are quite diversified depending on the agro-ecological zone. In the Sudan-Sahelian north, the agro-pastoral system predominates. It is characterized by the transhumance of part of the herds to the southern grazing areas in the dry season after the harvest. In the southern Sudanese-Guinean and central Sudanian regions, the agro-pastoral system predominates, with a predominance of agriculture (Richard et al., 2019).

4.2.3. Senegal

4.2.3.1. Niakhar

4.2.3.1.1. Description of biophysical variables

Niakhar site is located in Fatick region, in the center-west of the groundnut basin. It polarizes 378 villages, the largest of which are: Sob, Sorokh, Sanghaie, Tukar, Niakhar, Yenghele, Ghalagne Kop, Barry Sine, Diohine.

The Niakhar area is part of a relatively flat topographic landscape. Elevation variations are very small (3 to 15 m) in the southern part between the dunes and the lowlands. In the northern part, the relief is more marked with elevation variations from 3 to 33 m (Figure 10a). The drainage follows the low elevation areas. The area is strongly influenced by a relatively shallow (around 6-7 m) brackish to saline groundwater table, and salinisation of soils is an issue where capillary rise and evaporation are of importance (Faye et al., 2020).

As shown by Figure 10b, there exist four main soil types into the Niakhar site: i) Lixisols are dominant, being soils with a higher clay content in the subsoil than in the topsoil, due to pedogenetic processes (i.e., the migration of clays) leading to a clay horizon in the subsoil. They are mostly located in the southern part ; ii) Regosols are mineral soils very little evolved, they form a mosaic of landscape with Lixisols in the northern part of the study area ; iii) Gleysols and Ferralsols are poorly represented across the site and located in the south-east. Ferralsols are very developed soils while Gleysols are wetland soils, observed in low topographic areas.

The land cover map shows that the landscape consists mostly of crops, herbaceous vegetation, shrubs, and built-up areas. The cultivated areas are more prominent in the south, the northwest and around the built-up areas that are scattered throughout the site (Figure 10c).

Niakhar site is characterised by soil organic carbon stocks ranging from 2 to 18 g/kg (Figure 10d). The 2-10 g/kg range is found throughout the site, with some areas with a range of 10-18 g/kg.

Figure 10: Variation of biophysical variables at Niakhar site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

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4.2.3.1.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock Systems

In the Niakhar site and in particular in the village of Sob (taken as an example in this first version of the report), the landscape is composed of four main units: i) livestock range areas (residual forest, lowlands, path connecting lowlands), ii) bush fields (cultivated or fallow), iii) hut fields (continuously cultivated), and iv) human settlements. In 2014, bush lands and hut fields occupied 90% of the sob area, with *Faidherbia albida* dominating the woody vegetation (42%), livestock grazing areas 8%, and dwellings 2% (Duguy, 2016). The woody cover is diversified with more than 60 species in total, with *Balanites aegyptiaca* (11 %) and *Agoneissus leiocarpus* (9 %) being the most important one after *F.albida* (Ndao et al., 2021).

The hut fields are contiguous to the houses and are only cultivated with food crops essentially millet and exceptionally peanuts or another crop (Cirad, 2013). Located beyond this area, the bush fields constitute a mixture of food crops (e.g. millet), cash crops (e.g. groundnuts) and fallow land. They may be combined with other crops such as watermelon, cowpeas, sorghum, etc. Fallow land is not present in the hut fields (Duguy, 2016).

The herds are led by extensive breeding practices; free grazing is practiced in cultivated areas (consumption of crop residues left in the field) or on fallow land and rangeland. The nightly parking of herds on the hutches allows for their fertilization by direct restitution of the manure. It is essentially practiced with cattle, and mostly in the dry season. There are a few marginal cases of herd penning on the hutches for goats. In winter, when night penning is practiced, it is done on plots left fallow. Fallows are annual in this zone and represented about 3% of the agricultural area in 2014 (Duguy, 2016). Crop residues are harvested, stored, and then distributed to the animals. Similarly, manure is brought to the bush and hut fields by cart (Duguy, 2016). Transhumance to the region of Tambacounda has gained importance due to human and animal demography, but has led to conflict in the target regions. A recent shift towards agriculture has been observed (Nicolay and Djamen, 2021).

4.2.3.2. Ouarkhokh

4.2.3.2.1. Description of Biophysical variables

The Ouarkhokh area is located in the transition zone of the groundnut basin and the Ferlo.

The relief is a plateau, partially covered by dunes. The higher altitudes are around 62.5 m for the upper limit and about 2.5 m for the lower limit into the vast tableland located in the northeast of the study area (Figure 11a).

According to the ISRIC soil groups, the Ouarkhokh area is dominated by the Arenosols (Figure 11b). The main land cover classes in Ouarkhokh are grassland, rain-fed cropland, shrubland, tree open végétation and built-up area (Figure 11c).

The Ouarkhokh site has the lowest soil organic carbon content which varies between 2 and 10g/kg throughout the study area (Figure 11d).

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Figure 11: Variation of biophysical variables in the Ouarkhokh site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

4.2.3.2.2. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock Systems

In the area of Ouarkhokh, Toure and André (1989) had identified an agro-sylvopastoral system organized around dwellings, ponds, cultivated areas, fallows, rangelands, herbaceous vegetation and reforestation areas.

The cultivated areas are mainly located around the houses and along the valleys. These fields are usually grouped together, in order to facilitate surveillance against the herds. These are temporary and seasonal crops, grown on dior or deck dior soils. The cultivated species are mainly millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) or cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*). Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is poorly represented because the water requirements of the plant are no longer covered and the soils are too poor for such crop (Fall, 2014). During the dry season, these fields are used as livestock parks, where the animals benefit from crop residues and the fields from organic manure (Fall, 2014).

The fallow plots appear to be grouped together, and farmers abandon an area to fallow for the same number of years as it was cultivated. These fallow areas are grazed by animals raised for the needs of the domestic economy, i.e., horses, donkeys, sheep and goats.

The rangeland zone is a vast pastoral territory where agriculture gives way to livestock due to the irregularity of rainfall, the nature of the soils and the scarcity of water resources (Ndiaye, 2007). Also called the dieri, this area corresponds to a transhumance couloir used by animals from the Ferlo of the six boreholes (i.e., natural reserve located in the northern Ferlo) and the Senegal River Valley during the dry season. The large grazing land for livestock, consisting of herbaceous pastures, form the bulk of the fodder stock during the rainy season and at the beginning of the dry season. In order to free the Niakhar region dominated by croplands, herds stay in grazing land of Ouarkhokh during all the rainy season.

The classified forests and silvopastoral reserves serve as retreat areas for livestock during the rainy season, and are therefore elements for regulating conflicts between herders and farmers (Ndiaye, 2007). In the

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rainy season, watering is provided exclusively by ponds, while exchanges between herders in these areas and sedentary farming villages are very limited. Thus, the exploitation of agroforestry areas is carried out according to a defined periodicity, depending on the extent of cultivated lands.

4.2.3.3. Koussanar

4.2.3.3.1. Description of Biophysical variables

The site of Koussanar is located in the administrative region of Tambacounda. The climate is tropical-Sahelian with a rainy season from June to October and a dry season from November to May. The average temperature is 29.4°C.

The relief is relatively flat in the northwestern part, with higher altitude around 60 m. It is characterised in its eastern part by the presence of lowlands, slopes and plateau (Figure 12a).

The main types of soil identified in the Koussanar site are: i) Acrisols which are acidic soils, resulting from the alteration of acidic rocks and in particular strongly altered clays that undergo further degradation (Figure 12b). They are dominant in the Koussanar site and are located mainly in the central western parts; ii) Vertisols, which correspond to clay soils in depressions, are derived from sediments containing a high proportion of clays. These Vertisols are located in the low topographic zones, and present in the northern part and form a belt that crosses the study site in its eastern part ; iii) Gleysols are located around the Vertisols, and correspond to the slightly muddy soils that are found around the depressions; iv) Solonetz, rich in exchangeable ions Na^+ , Mg^{2+} ..., are located around the depressions in small areas; and v) Luvisols are derived from a wide variety of unconsolidated eolian, alluvial and colluvial materials, but also from physically altered silty stones. They are mainly located in the southern part of the Koussanar site.

As shown in Figure 12c, the Koussanar site can be divided into four land use-land cover units: shrubs, crops, herbaceous vegetation and gallery forests. The shrubs class occupies most of the area, followed by crops concentrated into depressions. Herbaceous vegetation is sparsely scattered across the area while the gallery forests are mainly located in the southeast.

In the Koussanar site, the lowest values of soil organic carbon are located in the low topographic zone (not exceeding 10g/kg) while in the high altitude areas, the quantity of SOC varies from 10 - 18g/kg (Figure 12d).

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Figure 12: Variation of biophysical variables in the Koussanar site: a) elevation, b) soil groups, c) land cover classes and d) soil organic carbon.

4.2.3.3.1. Inventory of Crops-Shrubs-Livestock Systems

Agro-silvopastoral systems are based on crop and fallow areas, rangeland areas, classified forests, ponds, boreholes, dwellings and the valley (Toure and André, 1989). The cultivated areas are located along the valley in the rangeland zone outside the classified forests. Two types of plots are distinguished in family farms: i) the collective plots which are for food crops (e.g. millet, sorghum, corn) for family consumption and the individual plots which are used for commercial crops.

The cultivated lands are organized into hut fields and bush fields. The hut fields form a first halo of cultivation around the village, while the bush fields far from the villages form the second halo. In bush fields, crops are rotated between peanuts, cotton, sorghum, and fallow land (Gelain, 2017). Because of the lack of land, the fallow is very short (~ 2 years) on most farms, especially on those without significant land potential. The plots adjoining the human settlements are permanently cultivated with maize and sometimes with millet. This is made possible by keeping livestock in this halo of crops during the dry season, thus maintaining fertility (Niang, 1987).

The inventory of woody vegetation in the fields identified 23 species in 12 families (Diouf, 2019). The most frequently encountered species are *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *Cordyla pinnata*, *Combretum glutinosum*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and *Sclerocarya birrea*.

According to Mbaye et al. (2003), animal manure is increasingly used to compensate for the lack of fertilizer and to cope with the general shortening of fallow periods. However, it must be said that the use of animal manure is still in its old form, which essentially consists of parking animals during the dry season on the fields closest to the concessions. The manure is essentially made up of the dung of cattle, sheep, goats, mules and horses.

4.3. Mapping of CSL systems across the study sites

4.3.1. Distribution of sites according to biophysical variables

The Principal Component Analysis carried out on the basis of the sites and environmental variables shows that two dimensions contain more than 80% of the information (Figure 13). The \cos^2 values vary from 0.75 to 0.90.

Figure 13 shows that all values of the studied environmental variables (i.e. aboveground biomass, trees and shrubs cover, elevation, rainfall and soil organic carbon) are positively correlated to the dim I axis, as well as the sites of Sikasso, Koulikoro and Tambacounda. This set is negatively correlated with the Niakhar-Ouarkokh group and the Saria-Yilou group. This means that these parameters are much higher in Sikasso, Koulikoro and Tambacounda than in the other sites (i.e. Niakhar-Ouarkokh and Saria-Yilou).

Figure 13: Principal Component Analysis of the sites and biophysical variables

4.3.2. Distribution of sites according to plant species and crop types

The Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA) between site and plant species/crop types shows that two axes contain more than 50% of the information, which are significant to interpret the results (Figure 14). Three groups were identified at the seven study sites:

- The Ouarkokh group, which is positively correlated with axis I with a \cos^2 greater than 0.75, containing the woody species *Combretum glutinosum* and *Accacia raddiana* combined with the groundnut as main crop.
- The Sikasso, Koulikoro and Niakhar group, which is negatively correlated with axis I, containing woody species which are *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Gliciridia sepium*, *Faidherbia albida* combined with crops such as millet, sorghum, cotton and maize.
- The Saria and Yilou group, which is negatively correlated with axis I with a \cos^2 greater than 0.75, containing the woody species *Piliostigma reticulatum*.

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- The Tambacounda group which is negatively correlated with axis 1 with a \cos^2 greater than 0.25 and the shrub species *Guiera Senegalensis* associated with livestock.

These results reflect clear differences between the sites. Indeed, Ouarkhokh is the driest site, as opposed to the other sites which are more humid (e.g. Tambacounda). *Guiera senegalensis* and the livestock system are present on all sites, hence their low correlation with the different axes. The Saria-Yilou group and the Sikasso-Kouloukoro group, on either side of the dim2 axis, and the Tambacounda-Niakhar group in the middle, mean that the characteristics of the latter overlap the first two groups. Indeed, the rainfall gradient decreases from Saria-Kilou to Kouloukoro-Sikasso. The associations between a plant species and a site mean that the presence of that species is stronger on this site than on another.

Figure 14: Correspondence Factor Analysis between sites and plant species

5. Conclusion and outlooks

This version of the Deliverable 7.1 presents an overall view of the landscape and existing CSL systems across the study area, and in detail into the seven sites of interest. Large amounts of geospatial data that inform on the environmental status were acquired processed and mapped for the characterisation of the landscapes. Information from a literature review allowed to describe and give a picture of the existing CSL systems throughout the seven sites. However, this information and the examination of the produced maps did not allow to draw final conclusion on the suitability of the sites for CSL systems. Additional data from WP4, 5 and 6 and outputs from the LUCIA model will be essential for this.

Moreover, in order to better feed the LUCIA model, detailed land use/cover mapping with *in situ* data and very high resolution satellite imageries from SPOT6-7 (5 m in multispectral and 1.5m in panchromatic) and/or Planet-Scope (3m) will be conducted for each of the sites from the end of the 2022-2023 growing season. In addition, field data from WP4, 5 and 6 (baseline surveys), once available, will be taken into account in the next version of this report. The site characterisation will also be deepened using dedicated methods for mapping agroforestry landscapes. Such techniques based on remote sensing, object-based segmentation, spatial analysis and unsupervised classification were used by Ndao et al. (2018) and Ndao et al. (2021) at the Niakhar site and could be extended to all remaining sites.

6. Appendix

Appendix 1: Presence and absence list of plant species, crops and activity types into the study sites

Site	Koulikoro	Sikasso	Niakhar	Ouarkhokh	Tambacounda	Yilou	Saria
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>			0	0	0	0	0
<i>Faidherbia albida</i>				0	0	0	0
<i>Guiera Senegalensis</i>					0		
<i>Piliostigma reticulatum</i>			0	0			
<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>			0	0	0	0	0
<i>Combretum glutinosum</i>	0	0	0		0	0	0
<i>Acacia radiana</i>	0	0	0		0	0	0
maize	0		0	0	0	0	0
cotton	0		0	0		0	0
sorghum		0	0	0	0	0	0
millet	0	0		0	0	0	0
groundnut	0	0	0		0	0	0
soil	0	0	0	0	0		
crop_yield	0	0	0	0	0		
Livestock							

Appendix 2: Mean value of biophysical variables computed from the 30 km x 30 km box of the study site

Site	Rainfall (mm)	Elevation (m)	AGB (kg/ha)	SOC (g/kg)	TreeCover (%)
Koulikoro	698.6	352.3	181.9	16.2	10.7
Sikasso	887.4	373.0	7875.1	11.0	13.1
Niakhar	478.0	10.2	3234.7	7.9	4.2
Ouarkhokh	394.6	44.9	3491.8	5.0	4.9
Tambacounda	612.6	40.2	311.5	12.0	12.8
Yilou	574.8	310.0	3011.4	8.4	8.5
Saria	627.7	313.0	3993.6	6.2	6.8

Appendix 3: Distribution of soil organic carbon across the SustainSahel countries

Appendix 4: Distribution of soil Nitrogen content across the SustainSahel countries

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Appendix 5: Distribution of soil texture classes across the SustainSahel countries

Appendix 6: Distribution of coarse fragments across the SustainSahel countries

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